

USE OF CHILDREN'S FOLK SONGS IN MUSIC CULTURE LESSONS

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Annotation: This article provides detailed information about the use of children's songs, types of children's songs and their analysis in music culture lessons in secondary schools.

Keywords: creativity, ability, music, interest, song, lesson, students, genre, education, school, pedagogue, national music.

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 " On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom", August 26, 2018 Resolution No. PD - 3920 " On measures for innovative development of the arts ", Resolution No. PD-4038 of November 28, 2018 " On approval of the Concept of further development of national culture in the Republic of Uzbekistan", are becoming increasingly important.[1]

The program "Musical education for secondary schools" was created based on the standards and requirements specified in the prospective state education standard.[2] My child's sense of sophistication education, national spirit, national music tunes as much as possible incorporating the content of necessary musical and practical skills in music acquisition is the main criterion of the program.

The program envisages the gradual implementation of the national values, traditions, folk creativity, musical heritage specific to Uzbekistan at the level of the child's ability to perceive, while preserving the existing pedagogical tasks. The works and music repertoires recommended in the program are aimed at students' perception of love for the Motherland, hard work, respect for nature, friendship, solidarity, compassion through musical images. In the methodology of musical education, the educational importance of singing is emphasized.

Folk songs and games that reflect the national culture help children to feel and perceive the world artistically and enjoy it. In particular, children of the elementary school will be taught the works "Oymomo tilla", "Olmajon", "Zuv-zuv borag'ay", "Kichkinajon kichkina" from children's folk songs, for the students of the upper class. "Oshxo'rakam kaptar", "Besh tosh", "O'ynaylik omon", "Bu bog'chada olisha", "Oq sholi, ko'k sholi", "Dasta-dasta", "Boychechak", "Qaldirg'och" during the year. study is recommended. [3] When teaching folk songs, the child's voice is just developing, the level of musical ability of the child, as well as proper education of artistic taste and connection to music it is necessary to take into account the need to meet their needs.

My child's quick and good learning of the song is music to the correct choice of the teacher's method of teaching singing depends. This method depends on the level of preparation of students can be different. The following is usually the teaching of singing steps are followed:

a) introductory interview; before starting to teach this song small talk to be held. To be learned in the introductory interview to the topic of the conversation without pre-announcing the content of the song to attract the children's attention, tell them: "Listen to the song and its tell me what the song is about" or "Listen to the song and determine how many couplets it consists of and a question like you need to think carefully about giving an assignment.

b) introduce the child to the song; teaching children to sing is the main work, and the work should leave a bright impression on the children when they first get acquainted with the work. If the children like the song, they get interested in this song and learn it easily. Music himself in the audience of children while his teacher sings the song rather than feeling like an artist singing in an auditorium it is necessary to approach work seriously. Because students are different they immediately notice the fakeness. [4]

c) conversation about the broadcasted song; music teacher conducts the second interview after the children listen to the song. In this conversation, the song is analyzed in detail and is unique in its structure aspects are explained within the scope of my child's theoretical knowledge. [5]

g) teaching the melody of the song; the teacher sings first read the text clearly and do not use words unfamiliar to the students explains the meaning. Have a child while teaching the melody they are required to listen carefully and are taught accordingly. [6]

d) work on the artistic performance of the song; song's passion performance improvement work begins at the time of teaching the song. Tone production, inhalation and exhalation, good ensemble', clear pronunciation is one of the elements of artistic performance of the song. Children will have a good impression if the music teacher plays the song himself. Teacher with his own voice he should be able to sing a folk song with warm feelings. Correct pronunciation of the text in folk songs is meaningful is the guarantee of singing. Perform each song with clear lyrics and fluency the main requirement is to correctly pronounce the text of the song plays an important role in revealing the artistic image.

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